

Mechanical Behaviors of Non-Crimp Fabric Composites Based on Multi-scale Analysis

T.Kurashiki^{1*}, K.Hamada¹, S.Honda¹, M.Zako¹, S.V.Lomov², and I.Verpoest²

1 Dept. of Management of Industry and Technology, Osaka Univ.,
2-1 Yamadaoka, Suita, Osaka, 565-0871, Japan

2 Dept. of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, K.U.Leuven,
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium

*Corresponding author: kurashiki@mit.eng.osaka-u.ac.jp

SUMMARY

In order to estimate the mechanical behaviors of Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF), the FE model of stitching yarn and laminates with resin-rich regions are generated individually, and the damage development under tensile loading is estimated based on the multi-scale analytical method. The numerical and experimental results are described.

Keywords: Non Crimp Fabric, Damage Development, Mesh Superposition Method

INTRODUCTION

Non Crimped Fabric (NCF) composites with stitching yarn have been attracted due to the formability and the improvement of out-of-plane strength, etc. Comprising a low manufacturing cost, NCF composites are currently being contemplated. However, NCF composites have many design parameters, such as fiber data, stitch structures, fiber orientation, and so on. In addition, the insertion of a yarn in the thickness direction causes displacements of the in-plane fibers. This leads to the formation of voids (resin pockets) in the stitch vicinity after impregnation. The resin-rich region may bring about the stress concentration and initiation of damage.

Furthermore, the estimation of damage development is very difficult, because matrix cracks and delamination at the crossover parts of fiber bundle may occur leading to complicated fracture modes in comparison with uni-directional fiber reinforced composites. If damages can be estimated with numerical simulation, it will become very useful tool for the estimation of mechanical properties of NCF composites.

For an evaluation of mechanical property of NCF composites with several parameters, FEM is one of effective methods in order to reduce the development times and the costs. Recently, several works have been reported in the literatures regarding FE-based model of NCF composites. Tserpes et al. reported a meso-mechanical approach of NCF composite structural parts based on RVE (representative volume elements) and homogenized progressive failure analysis [1]. Himmel et al. developed a FE based unit-cell model considering the thickness and fiber orientation of the layers and the shape and size of resin pockets [2]. Mikhaluk et al. reported a multi-scale FE homogenization to obtain effective mechanical properties of NCF composites with account of resin-rich zones and various fiber volume fraction values [3].

In this paper, the mesh superposition method, which is one of the multi-scale analytical methods of FEM, is applied. The FE model of stitching yarn and laminates with resin-rich regions for NCF composites are generated individually and FE analysis can be carried out by superposition of both models at the same time. The advantages of the mesh superposition method are that interaction between the laminate and a stitching yarn at the same time and that the mechanical behaviors of each mesh can be estimated by one step. The method is more convenient than the other multi-scale analytical methods such as the homogenization method and the zooming method. The damage development of NCF composites under tensile loading is estimated based on the multi-scale analytical method for the safety evaluation. The numerical and experimental results are described.

NUMERICAL METHOD

Figure 1 shows the scheme of the structure analysis of NCF composites by the proposed method. The geometrical data of NCF is generated by WiseTex software, which has been developed by Lomov S. V. et. al [4]. FE modeling of NCF is implemented by MeshTex, the FE modeling software for fiber reinforced composites developed by Zako, etc [5]. Since geometry of NCF is complex, it is not easy to generate FE models integrally. Therefore, stitching yarn part and laminates part are modeled individually. In order to consider the interaction of each part, the mesh superposition method is applied to the FE analysis.

Figure 1 Scheme of numerical modelling for NCF composites.

GEOMETRICAL MODELING

The geometrical model of NCF composites is separated a stitching yarn part and a laminate part. The former is determined with some input data such as kinds of fiber, volume fraction, diameters of cross sections, stitch structure, and stitch spacing. The latter is determined with fiber data, volume fraction, the number of ply, thickness, fiber orientation, and geometries of resin-rich region.

In the case of stitching yarn, the shapes and the path data of cross sections are calculated. In the case of laminates, the width of the resin-rich region of each ply is determined as multiple of the diameter of the stitching yarn, and the length is decided as multiple of the width. Resin rich region usually forms into diamond shapes called “Crack”. They become connected areas called “Channel” when the length are longer than stitch spacing. Examples of geometrical models generated by WiseTex are shown in Fig.2.

FE MODELING

In the MeshTex, FE models are generated with geometrical data acquired from WiseTex. In the case of stitching yarn, data of yarn path and cross section are given by WiseTex. As shown in Fig.3, all cross sections are divided into tetragonal elements, and linked each other along the vector of yarn direction to generate hexahedral elements. A unit cell area is moved in quarter stitch spacing because it is difficult to generate elements on crossover points of stitching yarns. The material properties of the each element are defined in the yarn direction as orthotropic anisotropy. Generated FE models of stitching yarn corresponding to NCF in Fig.2 are shown in Fig.4 for example.

Figure 3 Process of generation of yarn model.

Figure 4 FE models of stitching yarn.

In the case of laminates, it is important to consider the shapes of resin-rich region caused by stitching and the connections between each ply. In the system, the transmission data is created by overlapping the shapes of all layers as shown in Fig.5. It is divided into tetragonal elements, and pushed out in the thickness direction to generate hexahedral elements. For typical example, FE models of laminates corresponding to NCF in Fig.2 are shown in Fig.6. Detailed laminates FE model can be created accurately in this way if any parameters are changed.

Figure 5 Transmission data of laminates with resin-rich region

Figure 6 FE models of laminates

MESH SUPERPOSITION METHOD

Mechanical behavior of NCF composites is estimated with Mesh superposition method. The stitching yarn and the laminates are defined individually as local mesh and global mesh. The interaction of each model can be estimated by superposition of both meshes. The detail of the method is as follows.

Analytical area is divided into global area ($\Omega^G = \Omega \setminus \Omega^L$) and local area (Ω^L) as shown in Fig.7. Ω^G is the area where only global mesh is exists, and Ω^L is the area determined both global mesh and local mesh. The boundary between two meshes is defined as Γ^{GL} , and surface forces affect not Γ^{GL} but only the external boundary (Γ^S), because Ω^L is perfectly inside Ω^G . On those assumptions, the stiffness equation is represented as shown in Eq.(1).

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K^G] & [K^{GL}] \\ [K^{LG}] & [K^L] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{d^G\} \\ \{d^L\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F^S\} \\ \{0\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Each argument in Eq.(1) is indicated with the following equations.

$$\begin{aligned} [K^G] &= \int_{\Omega^G} [B^G]^T [D^G] [B^G] d\Omega \\ &+ \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^L] [B^G] d\Omega, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$[K^L] = \int_{\Omega^L} [B^L]^T [D^L] [B^L] d\Omega, \quad (3)$$

$$[K^{GL}] = \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^L] [B^L] d\Omega, \quad (4)$$

$$[K^{LG}] = \int_{\Omega^L} [B^L]^T [D^L] [B^G] d\Omega = [K^{GL}]^T, \quad (5)$$

$$[F^S] = \int_{\Gamma^S} [N^G]^T \{t\} d\Gamma. \quad (6)$$

Figure 7 Definition of analytical area

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To estimate an effect of microscopic geometry caused by stitching on failure development, the tensile test of NCF with in-situ observation by CCD camera has been carried out. The specimen has been prepared as glass fiber / polyester composites. Figure 8 shows the knitting pattern and geometry of a specimen for NCF composites. The laminate consisted of four plies and the stacking sequence is $[0/90]_s$. Stitching yarns consolidated two laminates with the stitching pattern 'tricot' as shown in Fig.8 and two stitched layers $[0/90]$ are laminated to each other symmetrically.

Figure 8 Knitting pattern of stitching yarn and size of test specimen

Figure 9 Damage development of NCF composites

Figure 9 shows the results of damage development investigated by CCD. The initial damage has appeared as transverse cracks in surface [0] layer when the strain has reached 0.25%. The transverse cracks have appeared around resin-rich region and the central region between stitching yarns as shown in Fig.9(a). The number of transverse cracks has increased as the strain also increased gradually. After no more new transverse crack appeared, splitting has occurred around the regions in [90] layer toward to loading direction as shown in Fig.9(b).

NUMERICAL RESULTS OF DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

In the simulation, the modeling of damage is very important. NCF composites are treated as heterogeneous bodies with anisotropy for fiber bundles and with isotropy for matrix, respectively. The isotropic damage model is applied for matrix, and anisotropic damage model is applied for the fiber bundle, respectively [6]. The occurrence of damage can be predicted by Hoffman's criterion.

To estimate the damage development of NCF composites, FE models for NCF composites have been prepared as shown in Fig.10. The model has the structure with considering the resin-rich zones, and the geometry of the resin-rich zone is obtained from the surface observation. The mechanical behavior under tensile loading had been estimated with the mesh superposition method. The periodic boundary condition has been considered both in x and y directions, and enforced strain has been applied in y direction.

(a) Schematic geometry of NCF composites

(b) Stitching yarn 'tricot' (c) GFRP laminate [0/90]s with opening resin region

Figure 10 FE models of NCF composites

Figures 11-13 show the numerical results of damage development for NCF composites. The colored parts represent the damaged elements judged by Hoffman's criterion. The initial damage has appeared when the strain reached 0.43% from the superposed stitching yarn as shown in Fig.11(a). The local stress concentration has been induced in [0] layer because of the effects of the resin-rich region and the superimposed stitching yarn, and the initial crack has appeared around the resin-rich region of [0] layer in Fig.11(b).

The sequential damage has appeared in the central region between stitching yarn of [0] layer in Fig.12(a) when the strain is 0.53%. And, there are no damages in [90] layer as shown in Fig.12(b). The position of the damage in [0] layer is almost same tendency with experimental results. The reason why the damage has occurred in the location is that the stress of the elements located at the central region is larger than that of the elements located the upper and lower parts of the resin-rich region.

Figure 13(a) shows that the damages develop in [0] layer. The splitting appeared and developed toward to loading direction in [90] layer when the strain is 0.91%.

Figure 11 Initial damage state of NCF composites (strain $\epsilon = 0.43\%$)

Figure 12 Damage state of NCF composites (strain $\epsilon = 0.53\%$)

(a) [0] layer

(b) [90] layer

Figure 13 Damage state of NCF composites (strain $\varepsilon = 0.91\%$)

Figure 14 shows the numerical and experimental results of stress-strain diagrams. There are same tendency with both results. Furthermore, the initial modulus of elasticity is also almost same. From the results, the mechanical behaviors of NCF composites can be estimated with the proposed multi-scale analytical method. And, it is very important to consider the resin-rich region and stitching yarn especially when the strength of NCF composites needs to be evaluated.

Figure 14 Comparison of Stress-Strain curves

CONCLUSION

For evaluation of mechanical properties of NCF composites, FE modeling system for NCF composites has been developed. In the system, the mesh superposition method is applied to FE analysis, and FE meshes of stitching yarn and laminates with resin-rich region are modeled individually. The geometrical data are determined by WiseTex, and FE models are generated by MeshTex.

From the numerical results with the developed system, the mechanical behaviors of NCF composites can be estimated with the proposed method. Though it is difficult to detect the strain level of the initial failure by the experiments, the strain of initial damage can be also evaluated conveniently with the proposed numerical simulation.

Furthermore, it is recognized that the consideration of geometry of NCF composites such as stitching yarn and resin-rich region are important to analyze the stress and strain of NCF. And, the mesh superposition method is very convenient for the estimation of mechanical behaviors of stitching yarns and laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study is sponsored by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS), "Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research", subject No.19656026.

References

- [1] Tserpes, K.I., et al., Mesomechanical analysis of non-crimp fabric composite structural parts, *Composite Structures*, 87, (2009), 358-369.
- [2] Himmel, N., et al., Elastic constants estimation of stitched NCF CFRP laminates based on a finite element unit-cell model, *Composites Science and Technology*, 67, (2007), 1081-1095.
- [3] Milhaluk, D.S., et al., Experimental observations and finite element modelling of damage initiation and evolution in carbon/epoxy non-crimp fabric composites, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 75, (2008), 2751-2766.
- [4] Lomov S.V. et al., Virtual textile composites software Wisetex, *Composite Science and Technology*, 65, (2005), 2563-74.
- [5] Zako, M., Kurashiki, T., et al., Damage development of woven composites based on multi-scale analysis, *ICCM-16*, (2007), CD-ROM.
- [6] Zako M., Uetsuji Y., Kurashiki T., Finite element analysis of damaged woven fabric composite materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, 63, (2003), 507-516.